

Department of Mathematics and Computer Science
Bachelor of Data Science

Domain Analysis of Jupyter Notebooks using NLP

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Contents

1	Introduction	2
2	Research Question	3
3	Related Work	4
4	Original Dataset	6
5	Experimental Setup and Approach	8
5.1	Research Question 1 (RQ1)	8
5.2	Research Question 2 (RQ2)	11
5.3	Ethical Considerations	13
6	Results	15
6.1	RQ1	15
6.2	RQ2	21
7	Discussions	27
7.1	Domain Classification Performance and Model Robustness	27
7.2	Embedding Model Performance and Semantic Representation	27
7.3	Code Complexity Analysis and Domain Relationship	28
7.4	Multicollinearity and Feature Selection	28
7.5	Implications for Practitioners and Researchers	28
8	Threats to Validity	29
8.1	External	29
8.2	Internal	29
9	Conclusion and Future Work	30
10	Data Availability	31
11	Appendix	37
11.1	Prompt for Qualitative Analysis	37
11.2	System Instruction for Qualitative Analysis	37
11.3	LLM Multi-Threading Implementation	37
11.4	AST for Tensor Complexities	37

Abstract

Jupyter Notebooks proliferate across diverse domains but lack effective classification systems. This study analyzed 1,049 tensor-themed Jupyter Notebooks from Kaggle using natural language processing for domain classification and softmax regression for correlation analysis between code complexity and the domain. Salient term extraction methods (LDA, BOW, TF-IDF) were applied across intrinsic features (code, in-line comments, Markdown narrative) with BERT, Word2Vec, and GloVe embeddings. BERT significantly outperformed other embeddings but showed semantic limitations. Code complexity metrics achieved poor domain prediction with a balanced accuracy of 0.144. Results demonstrate that semantic analysis with contextual embeddings shows promise but requires domain-specific fine-tuning, while traditional code metrics prove insufficient for notebook domain classification.

1 Introduction

Traditionally, tasks such as data visualization, statistical analysis, and machine learning (ML) were often performed using expensive proprietary software like MATLAB, SAS, and IBM SPSS [48]. To mitigate the downsides of these tools, IPython was created which later evolved into Jupyter Notebooks as one of the remedies [65]. Nonetheless, there has also been increasing popularity in the aspect for presenting and visualising well written code in the domain of literate programming, where Jupyter Notebooks are applicable as well [21, 33]. These notebooks, in contrast to traditional Python scripts, have grown in popularity of presenting code across different intersections of computer science, data science, ML and education [21]. Another study published that Jupyter Notebooks have allowed to provide a narrative approach to programmers to present their findings which would not have been possible with traditional scripts [27].

However, the lack of systematic domain classification in these notebooks causes caveats in organising and reproducing them because there is difficulty in determining the correctness of notebooks since certain notebooks from the data analysis domain may require more testing than other domains [53]. Furthermore, the importance of researching the domain classification of Jupyter Notebooks stems from the widespread adoption of neural networks and large language models (LLMs), which are extensively implemented and developed within Jupyter Notebook [38], particularly in sectors such as healthcare and education, a trend accelerated significantly since the release of ChatGPT in 2022 and subsequent ML models [28]. Given that these advanced computational tools heavily utilize tensors and various linear algebra operations, understanding their implementation becomes essential, as these operations constitute the backbone of modern deep learning models [67]. Notably, a comprehensive analysis of 1.4 million notebooks revealed `numpy`, a library optimized for tensor manipulation, as the most frequently used library (see Figure 1), underscoring the relevance of tensor-based computations in Jupyter Notebooks [52]. Moreover, the inherently complex and multi-dimensional nature of tensors highlights the necessity for interactive, visual-oriented tools such as Jupyter Notebooks, which facilitate better visualization, comprehension, and efficient computation through clearly segmented code cells. Additionally, these notebooks enable users to leverage powerful features within the Jupyter and Python ecosystems, including JupyterHub, IPyWidgets, IPython “magic” commands, Dask, and IPyParallel, allowing for direct and interactive management of backend computational tasks [14].

Reliance on Jupyter Notebooks introduces critical challenges related to reproducibility and execution, such as missing dependencies, out-of-order cell execution, and frequent errors like `ImportError` [52]. Understanding a notebook’s domain is crucial because different domains have different requirements for reproducibility and execution. For instance, notebooks utilized in research and development (R&D) settings often demand precise cell execution order to maintain integrity, whereas mismanagement could result in inaccurate outcomes, thus undermining the reliability of research findings and potentially propagating erroneous conclusions to subsequent

Figure 1: Top 15 Imports [52]

studies. Identifying such flaws can be done more efficiently if it has been identified which notebooks are used in the domain of R&D because it narrows down the search time for finding the notebooks that needs to be investigated, allowing for faster iterations. Therefore, it is of utmost importance that it is known which notebook belongs to which domain. The presence of these notebooks across different fields brings us to the overarching research question, **Which domain does a tensor-themed Jupyter Notebook belongs to?**; that aims at classifying the Jupyter Notebooks by its domain specifically with a focus on notebooks containing tensors which is an essential component in training ML models like neural networks [62], transformers [67] and other linear algebra computations.

This thesis will use a dataset of tensor-related Jupyter Notebooks mined from Kaggle [68]. On this dataset, extensive lexical and syntactic analysis will be done with the help of a variety of relevant algorithms that can be used for classifying these notebooks to their domain.

2 Research Question

In order to answer the overarching question, two sub questions are formulated. Firstly, **what are the predominant domains of tensor-themed Jupyter Notebooks based on their code & textual content?** This question aims at leveraging natural language processing (NLP) to determine the domains of a notebook. Textual content of a notebook such as intrinsic features like in-line comments, Markdown narrative and the code, can be used to identify salient and latent terms that may reveal the notebook’s intended application using NLP. In a study by Grotov et al., it was found that notebooks were much longer than traditional scripts, as they allowed users to add more information through Markdown cells [21]. This highlights their relevance for literate programming, extending beyond the capabilities of traditional scripts, which only allow in-line comments and docstrings. Thus, the textual content from Markdown narrative and comments may help in revealing the underlying domains. Whereas, the code in the notebooks will contain relevant keywords present in docstrings or variable names that will further help in determining the domain [57].

To further explore the relationship between code and the respective domains of Jupyter Notebooks, this thesis will explore, **to what extent does the code complexity such as its number of lines, library usage, size of narrative, tensor complexities (that is, different tensor operations and total number of operations), number of functions and classes, depth of inheritance and cyclomatic complexity correlate with their respective broader domains as defined in the previous question?** This question is relevant as it focuses on the structural and syntactic integrity of the code rather than the textual features, which is the focus

of the previous research question. Research by Li et al. has established that code complexity metrics can serve as predictive indicators for software characteristics and domain-specific patterns [31].

3 Related Work

Textual and Semantic Based Approaches for Domain Classification

- **Domain-Analysis of Software Systems and GitHub Repositories**

The paper by Capiluppi et al. [8] showcases how lexicon can be used for source code analysis. In the project, the focus is on 50 Java projects where the lexicon is extracted from the source code as well as the description of each project (ReadMe file). Through this lexicon extraction, they were able to perform lexical analysis using Latent Dirichlet allocation (LDA) for obtaining one or more application domain. Although, this paper uses lexicon, which is similar to the first research question's scope, the methodology described by Capiluppi differs slightly from this thesis. More detailed explanation for the methodology of this thesis is provided in Section 5. Firstly, this paper involves a pre-defined set of domains which is limited to 20, as opposed to this thesis' focus on using domains defined via Kaggle tags which amounts to 144. Secondly, the paper uses 10 experts to evaluate the domain which can be prone to human error due to subjective evaluation, as opposed to the approaches without human bias such as using cosine similarity between the vectors of text and domain, which will be used in this thesis' methodology. Another study by Zanartu et al. [1] dived into domain classification of GitHub repositories. The extracted features for this study included description of the repository, ReadMe file, topic tags, license, programming language, contributors and sub-folders/files. This study includes manually annotated repositories which makes the domain classification easier. Then, they use LinearSVM to employ important terms from the extracted lexicon which is then passed into Fast and Lightweight AutoML (FLAML) for finding the best classifier which was found to be Light Gradient Boosted Machine (LGBM). The results from this study highlighted the significant importance of textual features, especially the ReadMe files. Thus, it can be expected that the Markdown narrative in the Jupyter Notebooks will be significantly influential in classifying the domain. However, due to the unsupervised nature of the problem in this thesis, the methodology for domain classification will differ from this paper.

- **Topic Modelling on Public Repositories**

The paper by Markovtsev et al. [39] describes a topic modelling approach in public repositories by analysing 13.6 million repositories. This work aligns with the intention of topic modelling for the first research question but is limited in scope. In their work, the authors use a BOW model to get the embeddings followed by an additive regularised topic model (ARTM) for topic modelling. They conclude the paper by manually sorting the labelled topics in 6 groups. This research paper, too, differs from the intention of this thesis. Firstly, using BOW model and ARTM limits the scope by treating words with bias and giving more importance to words that appear more frequently. In cases like this thesis, where data is limited, this may be harmful. Thus, LDA and TFIDF are also employed to account for word frequency in the notebook and across the whole dataset. More details about LDA and TFIDF can be found in Section 5. Additionally, the aim is to classify the salient terms from these extracted topics into the respective domains rather than categorising the topics into groups.

- **Classifying Extra Domains beyond the Ground Truth**

The paper by Sas et al. [57] discussed the caveats of relying on ReadMe files as a proxy for projects as seen previously. They suggest a focus on source code to ensure that the information about a project is retained while doing domain-analysis. They focus on moving

Figure 2: Distribution Graph for Labels for a GitHub Project [57]

from a project-level focus to a file-level focus to annotate their domain and employ a weak labelling approach based on keyword extraction, which aligns in answering the first research question. Their goal is to identify the semantic components in software projects that can be then used for reversed semantic engineering, reusable code and more. They use TFIDF to extract the keywords from the project and then use GitHub topics as domains. For analysis, they employ distribution graph with all the domains on the x-axis and likelihood for a project belonging to that label in the y-axis. This graph can be seen in Figure 2. This paper aligns closely in answering the first research question of this thesis and the methodology described, particularly the TFIDF-based keyword extraction and weak labelling approach for domain annotation, acts as an inspiration for this thesis. Building on their use of GitHub topics, this thesis adopts Kaggle tags as domains (i.e., ground truth), which can provide more comprehensive and realistic annotations than establishing a pre-defined, manually created list of domains. More details about using Kaggle tags as a ground truth can be found in Section 5.

- **$P@k$ to Evaluate Weakly Supervised Models**

The paper by Zhang et al. [70] discusses weakly supervised multi-label classification of scientific papers. This paper uses $P@k$ and $NDCG@k$ for evaluating the top k predicted labels which can act particularly useful for weakly supervised problems like the first research question. Since this thesis will use Kaggle tags as the ground truth (see Section 5), using $P@k$ can be a limitation because Kaggle tags are sparse amongst Jupyter Notebooks. That is, not all notebooks have tags and every notebook has varying number of tags. Thus, notebooks that have no tags at all or different predicted domains than the truth at $P@k$ will be penalised more harshly, even though these domains are relevant but they do not match the ground truth (i.e. Kaggle tags). The dynamic nature of the domains across different notebooks makes it undesirable to use $P@k$ as a standalone evaluation metric.

Code Complexity Metrics and Domain Correlation Analysis

- **Source Code Classification using Abstract Syntax Trees (AST)**

The paper by Parvathy et al. [49] describes using AST for extracting the structure of source code for further classification. Although, the scope of the second research question is not classification, the usage of AST in this paper is relevant. This paper found that using AST for classification of source code resulted in 99.5% to classify code fragments according to predetermined categories based on their functionality, highest amongst other techniques discussed in the paper. Therefore, it can be expected that AST will be an effective method in this thesis' methodology for second research question in getting tensor complexities because it can better capture the hierarchical relationships and structural information in source code, unlike methods like token-based neural networks as discussed in the paper.

- **Code Understandability Analysis in Jupyter Notebooks**

The paper by Ghahfarokhi et al. [19] follows a similar approach that can be incorporated for this thesis for solving the second research question. That is, the authors analyse two groups of metrics that they call notebook-based and script-based metrics. They extensively define metrics like lines of code, number of parameters, number of comment words etc. but for the purpose of this thesis, a subset of these metrics are taken because most of the metrics may show signs of multicollinearity. For example, for regression, having number of statements and lines of code as independent variables can be problematic as number of statements has a linear relationship with lines of code (i.e. if number of statements increase, the lines of code increases) which can cause these variables to not be fully independent; therefore, it is better to have only lines of code as an independent variable rather than having both. The study by Ghahfarokhi however, differs from this thesis in analysis objective. The authors focus on qualitative study of code understandability whereas, the focus in this thesis is on quantitatively studying the correlation of code metrics with domain.

- **Analysing Object-Oriented Design Metrics for Predicting Severity Faults**

Building on the limitations and differences in the objectives of the paper by Ghahfarokhi et al., Zhou et al. [72] investigated the objective of probabilistic classification of code. This aligned well with the requirements for answering the second research question; however, the authors explored a binary classification to predict fault-proneness rather than a multiclass classification. Despite this, the methodology employed in this paper closely aligns with the methodology of this thesis described in Section 5. The authors focus on object oriented (OO) design of the code and use OO related metrics for their analysis. They use a multivariate regression with OO metrics as independent variable and target variable being high or low severity faults. For this thesis, a multivariate regression will be used; and the scope of the metrics for this thesis will be beyond OO metrics because other parts of code will be analysed, such as size of narrative as well. The multivariate analysis will be incorporated into the softmax regression for finding the primary domain of the notebook.

- **Cyclomatic Complexity (CC) and Lines of Code (LOC) Relationship**

The paper by Smith et al. [2] describes an important aspect of code metrics that was also discussed previously which is multicollinearity. In the paper, the authors find a relationship between CC and LOC highlighting that many code metrics may show a relationship between each other which may not be limited to CC or LOC. Another study by Landman et al. [30] focusing on a large corpus of Java methods found a similar linear trend between CC and LOC. Therefore, this paper acts as an inspiration to employ collinearity check before doing a statistical analysis for answering second research question. The authors emphasise that the models that do not bind LOC and CC as multicollinear will have unstable explanatory power. Therefore, it is important to check for such relationships between the code metrics and employ measures like omitting to avoid multicollinearity [10].

4 Original Dataset

The dataset of Jupyter Notebooks are mined from Kaggle which is a platform renowned for hosting data science competitions and analytical notebooks [68]. The collection process employs a systematic approach targeting Kaggle notebooks containing the string 'tensor' in the name. The collected data maintains a hierarchical structure with a root directory containing subdirectories for each Kaggle user, further divided into individual notebook directories. Each notebook directory contains the original .ipynb file along with a `kernel-metadata.json` file that stores valuable metadata including keyword tags. At the time of extraction (April 2025), 1,049 tensor-themed notebooks were extracted from 736 different authors spanning diverse application domains, as inferred from the names of the notebooks, using this collection methodology. As seen in Figure 3, approximately 73.3% of notebooks in the dataset contain at least one Kaggle tag indicating that there exists ground truth for the majority of the notebooks and this can be helpful for the

quantitative analysis. The use of Kaggle tags as ground truth, taken from Sas et al. [57], was discussed previously in Section 3. On the contrary, however, since there are some notebooks without ground truth, a qualitative analysis is required to verify whether the predicted domains hold. The dataset encompasses 144 unique tags in total providing a rich foundation for domain classification analysis. Figure 4 shows the distribution of most occurring Kaggle tags across the dataset and Figure 5 shows the distribution of number of Kaggle tags across the notebooks.

Figure 3: Number of Jupyter Notebooks with Kaggle Tag(s)

Figure 4: Frequency of Kaggle Tags Across the Dataset

Figure 5: Number of Kaggle Tags Across Notebooks

5 Experimental Setup and Approach

5.1 Research Question 1 (RQ1)

Salient Terms Extraction

Initially, the notebooks will be preprocessed to extract the Markdown narrative, in-line comment, library usage and the code. The first question would involve using a LDA approach to find salient terms from latent topics and narrow down the labelling process of the extracted content of the notebook in order to find their domain. LDA is commonly used for topic modelling in the scientific realm [71]. LDA can provide the list of salient terms that are reliable while consuming less time and requiring low compute. For the purposes of this thesis, LDA will be implemented based on the paper of Hoffman et. al. [22] because of its efficient and fast convergence with excellent performance on text data for topic retrieval. In the paper, it was found that the perplexity of the LDA decreased exponentially with time leading to a fast convergence, thus showing good performance. The LDA model as described by Hoffman et al. operates on the assumption that documents are mixtures of topics, where each topic is characterized by a distribution over words. The algorithm works by first drawing topic proportions for each document from a Dirichlet distribution, then for each word in the document, it draws a topic assignment based on the document’s topic proportions, and finally draws the actual word from the selected topic’s word distribution. The online variational inference approach optimizes a variational objective function that approximates the true posterior distribution, making it computationally efficient for large datasets. The algorithm uses stochastic gradient ascent to update the global topic-word distributions, incorporating a learning rate that balances between new and previously learned information. For this thesis, the approach is similar to the one described by IBM where a LDA model is used using libraries like Gensim in Python [25].

Salient terms will be extracted individually from intrinsic features such as in-line comments, Markdown narrative, and code. These salient terms will be stored and processed separately to see if a trained model from these isolated extracts provided a better performance than all of these intrinsic features combined. Other methods for salient term extraction will also be explored, such

as using TFIDF for term frequency while being robust to common stopwords and giving priority to rare words [3] or using BOW which is measure of word frequency in the dataset [18].

TFIDF is a simpler approach that can be formulated as:

$$\text{TF-IDF}(t, d) = \text{TF}(t, d) \times \text{IDF}(t)$$

where t refers to a term in the notebook and d refers to a particular document, i.e., notebook in this case.

$\text{TF}(t, d)$ refers to the frequency of term t in the document d and can be defined as:

$$\text{TF}(t, d) = \frac{\text{Number of occurrences of term } t \text{ in document } d}{\text{Total number of terms in document } d}$$

$\text{IDF}(t)$ is the inverse document frequency and can be defined as:

$$\text{IDF}(t) = \log \left(\frac{N}{1 + |\{d \in D : t \in d\}|} \right)$$

For example, words like “the” will have lower weightage despite their frequent occurrence because of their less informative nature.

BOW for salient terms is a much simpler approach than LDA and TF-IDF as it merely calculates the frequency of a word in a document, i.e., notebook. The BOW representation can be formulated as:

$$\text{BOW}(t, d) = \text{count}(t, d)$$

where $\text{count}(t, d)$ represents the number of occurrences of term t in document d . For a document d with vocabulary V , the BOW vector is:

$$\text{BOW}(d) = [\text{count}(t_1, d), \text{count}(t_2, d), \dots, \text{count}(t_{|V|}, d)]$$

Words like ‘the’ will receive more weightage due to their high frequency of occurrence across documents.

TFIDF will be implemented by using `scikit-learn`’s `TfidfVectorizer()` [64], which converts a collection of raw documents into a matrix of TF-IDF features. On the other hand, BOW requires counting the number of terms which can be done intuitively with a hashmap.

Embeddings

Following the salient terms, an open source and pre trained version of Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) (`bert-base-uncased`) embedding model will help to label the notebooks with their corresponding domain as it is widely used and is trained on large corpora of English including all of English Wikipedia and 11,038 unpublished books from `BookCorpus` [4, 20]. BERT is capable of contextualised embeddings which helps in creating embeddings for words based on their context [58]. The BERT architecture includes token, positional and segment embeddings [12]. Positional and segment embeddings are irrelevant as the focus is on the individual and independent word tokens. By default, segment embeddings default to 0, as well as positional embeddings. The input for the embedding model will be the salient terms in the notebook [66], which will be tokenised into embeddings along with the predefined list of broader domains, which will act as the ground truth. This technique of predefining domains is known as weak labelling, as mentioned previously. In contrast to manual labelling each notebook with respect to their domain, weak labelling ensures scalability; that is, instead of iterating through each notebooks manually, one can label use the predefined labels and classify each notebook to one of the label which will be computationally faster as cosine similarity can be used to determine this. However, using a predefined list of domains derived from the notebooks’ tags also causes a

limitation as it does not include all domains that may be feasible beyond the ones mentioned in the Kaggle tags.

An example of the implementation of BERT and its evaluation can be found at a GitHub repository¹. The output of BERT encodings will then be used to calculate the cosine similarity between the domain and the salient terms in order to label the notebook with the domains they belong to. The domains will be ranked based on the cumulative sum of cosine similarity across all the salient terms. The reason cosine similarity was chosen is due to its superior nature in calculating similarity as compared to other methods like Jaccard similarity or Euclidean distance because it is robust to length of the documents [59].

Other embeddings such as GloVe and Word2Vec can be implemented in a similar fashion. They are additional algorithms to be employed for creating word embeddings. Word2Vec is effective for capturing out-of-vocabulary words with the help of sub-words, which can be useful for this thesis as there is limited data with limited vocabulary [54]. Additionally, the paper by Rakshit et al. states that "GloVe embedding technique inherits a powerful property to handle the occurrence of low frequency words in a dataset it performs this task" making it a suitable embedding technique for the task at hand with limited data and potentially low frequency words [54]. Using pre trained models like `fse/word2vec-google-news-300` and `fse/glove-wiki-gigaword-100`, the desired results can be achieved. Both of these models are trained on large datasets, where the former is trained on 100 billion words from the `Google News Dataset` and the latter is trained on 2 billion `Twitter tweets` making them appropriate to use [17, 16].

Evaluation Metrics

Once all the predicted domains of the notebooks are collected, quantitative analysis can be done by ranking these predicted domains in decreasing order of similarity to determine the most prevalent domains and then match the first k domains with the k domain tags from Kaggle for that notebook, where $k \geq 0$. As mentioned in Section 3, this evaluation metric is what is known as $P@k$ and this gives us a measure of the accuracy of domain prediction. For this thesis, the chosen k is 3 in order to reflect different real-world relevant domains where the notebook may belong. If the notebook does not have Kaggle tags (i.e. no ground truth) or less than k tags, qualitative analysis can be done directly because the $P@k$ score will always evaluate to less than 1 (or 0 in cases where there is no ground truth) as there is not enough ground truth to be compared to. Discarding the notebooks with insufficient tags is also undesirable since it will cause a loss of 611 notebooks (see Figure 5) which is more than 55% of the dataset. Dynamic k values, depending on the ground truth availability, will also be avoided to ensure consistency in comparison across different notebooks and if $P@k$ relies on varying denominator (i.e. k), there can be high variance in the results making them unreliable. Furthermore, in cases such as different predicted versus ground truth in the first k ordering, $P@k$ will also give a low score indicating a low accuracy despite the relevance of these extra domains predicted beyond the ground truth. Therefore, it is necessary to have a complementing qualitative analysis.

For the qualitative analysis, a LLM, `llama3-8b-8192`, will be used for checking relevance of all the predicted domains of a notebook because of its lightweight nature and high-volume processing capability of data due to a large token window [35]. A prompt (see Appendix Section 11.1) and system instruction (see Appendix Section 11.2), designed in accordance to the prompt guidelines of MIT [13], will be used to ensure that the following question pertaining to the specificity and relevance of the domain are answered by the LLM:

"Based on the notebook content, is the given domain relevant to this notebook and

¹NielsRogge. "Fine tuning BERT (and friends) for multi label text classification." *Transformers-Tutorials*. GitHub. <https://github.com/NielsRogge/Transformers-Tutorials>

determine whether it is highly relevant, partially relevant or just relevant- and explain why? How specific & precise are the domains? Are they too general (e.g. data analysis) or appropriate specific (e.g. NLP) or too specific (e.g. tensor)-choose one and explain?"

The input for the qualitative assessment will be the content of the Jupyter Notebooks and the predicted domains. To process multiple notebooks simultaneously and enable time-efficiency, multithreading will be used by invoking the model simultaneously on 5 workers. The implementation for multithreading can be seen in Appendix Section 11.3. Complementing the LLM, there will be a manual check done to verify the validity of the predicted domains and also have human intervention.

Figure 6 shows a visualisation of the experimental flow.

Figure 6: Flow Chart of Pipeline for answering RQ1

5.2 Research Question 2 (RQ2)

Code Complexity Algorithm

For answering the second question, As mentioned in Section 2, an algorithm will be implemented to explore the correlation between code metrics and the broader domains identified in the previous question. In order to do this, the algorithm will work in combinations of regular expression, formulae and AST, which is a tree data structure that can be used to break down code of Jupyter Notebook into smaller fragments for calculating more complex aspects of the code. Due

their nature, AST are good for follow-up code-related tasks like classification [60].

The notebook content will first be preprocessed to clean and normalize text by removing cell separators and metadata across different cell types. For tensor complexities, AST parsing will be prioritized over regex where possible, as AST provides a more syntactically accurate understanding of code structure and is robust to style variations [49, 60]. However, a regex fallback mechanism will be included for handling code that may contain IPython magics or syntax errors. The implementation for the AST to retrieve tensor operations can be seen in Appendix Section 11.4.

Several complexity dimensions will be analyzed: non-empty lines of code will be counted, lines of Markdown narrative will be counted, library usage will be extracted through `import` statement detection with special emphasis on tensor related libraries (numpy, tensorflow, torch, etc.), and tensor operations (matmul, reshape, transpose, etc.) will be identified using AST node visitors. The list of relevant tensor libraries are obtained from the study by Panagakis et al. [63] and the list of tensor operations are obtained from the official TensorFlow documentation [23]. Function and class definitions will be quantified to assess modularization practices. Regular expressions can be used to parse the notebook for information like number of lines, library usage, narrative size, number of function and classes. For deeper structural analysis, inheritance depth will be estimated by mapping parent-child class relationships recursively, and cyclomatic complexity will be calculated using the $E - N + 2P$ formula, where E represents control flow graph edges, N represents nodes, and P represents connected components [55, 42].

The implementation will target tensor-related operations to understand the technical complexity of machine learning notebooks. These metrics will be converted into one-hot encoded features where appropriate (e.g., library usage) while maintaining numerical values for metrics like line counts and cyclomatic complexity. The extracted metrics will then be combined with the domain classification results from the first research question by taking the top-1 domain per notebook. Each notebook will be parsed individually and the results will be compiled into a `pandas DataFrame`, providing the foundation for statistical analysis of correlations between code metrics and notebook domains.

Softmax Regression

To address multicollinearity in the code metrics, a two-stage feature selection approach will be employed. Firstly, the pairwise multicollinearity analysis will be done to identify highly correlated feature pairs with correlation coefficient ≥ 0.8 using `DataFrame.corr` because collinearity above 80% is said to be high [15]. After this, the method of omitting variables is used to ensure that multicollinearity does not affect the interpretation of the results. In the second stage, the Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) is calculated for the remaining features, removing those with $VIF > 10.0$ to further reduce multicollinearity [56]. This is done using `variance_inflation_factor` function from the `statsmodels.stats.outliers_influence` package. This process ensures the model's stability by preventing inflated variance in coefficient estimation, which is particularly important in multinomial regression where coefficient interpretability impacts domain relationship analysis. The final feature set is then normalized using `StandardScaler` before model training.

In the `DataFrame` containing the extracted code features, the corresponding ground truth will be added, additionally. The ground truth, in this case, is the domain predicted with the highest cosine similarity across the predefined list of domains per notebook. To model this multi-class classification problem, a softmax regression using `scikit-learn's LogisticRegression()` with `multi_class='multinomial'` for handling multiple classes and `class_weight='balanced'` for handling class imbalance will be implemented [36]. Softmax can take the form of one-versus-the-rest which creates coefficients per class [32]. The reason softmax regression is chosen is due to its explainable nature and simplicity and unified modelling approach, allowing for modelling all

classes simultaneously [32]. On the contrary, in one-versus-one, one would need to model a binary regression for each possible pairs of classes which is computationally expensive.

Evaluation Metrics

For evaluating the softmax regression model, the selected metrics are specifically designed for imbalanced multi-class classification problems, eliminating the need for qualitative analysis. Firstly, a balanced accuracy using `scikit-learn`'s `balanced_accuracy_score` as the primary metric will be employed, which calculates the average of recall obtained on each class [6]. Unlike conventional accuracy, balanced accuracy gives equal weight to each class regardless of its frequency in the dataset, preventing majority classes from dominating performance because it is likely for real-world datasets, like Jupyter Notebooks from Kaggle, to be imbalanced [9]. Additionally, macro-averaged F1 score using `scikit-learn`'s `f1_score` with `average='macro'` will be utilised, which independently calculates precision and recall for each class before averaging across all, giving equal importance to all classes [46].

These metrics are used together as they go hand-in-hand with each other. Balanced accuracy can provide the average recall (sensitivity) for each class, thus giving the ratio of correctly identified instances of all classes; whereas, F1 score with macro-average can provide the harmonic mean of precision and recall, thus giving insights on balancing precision-recall concerns for all the classes. F1 score can provide a higher-level view on the performance across the classes.

Figure 7 shows a visualisation of the experimental flow.

5.3 Ethical Considerations

There are several ethical considerations in the described approach. Firstly, using pre-trained Kaggle tags can cause limitations to the scope of domains identified because only tensor-related notebooks are mined as part of the dataset and thus, only the Kaggle Tags obtained from these notebooks are considered as ground truth. This raises an ethical concern of representation bias because of the limited scope [44]. Additional sources like GitHub topics and Wikidata could be used to add more general and specific topics [57].

Secondly, using pre-trained models for creating embeddings and evaluation in the first research question raises important ethical concerns about algorithmic fairness and representation. These models are trained on specific datasets that may not adequately represent diverse domains, research communities, or linguistic patterns found in Jupyter Notebooks. When applied to underrepresented content, these models could systematically disadvantage certain research areas or communities whose work differs from the mainstream patterns captured in the training data. This creates an equity issue where some domains receive more accurate classification than others, potentially affecting resource allocation, research visibility, or automated content curation systems. To address these fairness concerns, human oversight and diverse validation approaches should be implemented to ensure equitable treatment across different research domains and communities.

Thirdly, to benchmark performance of multiple models for extracting salient terms and computing embeddings, followed by using LLM for qualitative evaluation requires heavy compute and raises concerns about research accessibility and environmental responsibility. For this thesis, an Apple M2 Pro chipset was used with 12 cores CPU; this creates barriers to entry that may exclude researchers from resource-constrained institutions or developing regions from conducting similar analyses. This digital divide perpetuates inequalities in research capabilities. Additionally, the environmental impact of running large language models repeatedly for evaluation purposes raises sustainability concerns. To promote more environmentally responsible research practices, `meta-llama/Llama-3.2-3B` can be used instead of `llama3-8b-8192` because it has 3 billion pa-

Figure 7: Flow Chart of Pipeline for answering RQ2

rameters compared to the 8 billion parameter [34].

6 Results

6.1 RQ1

On applying all the combinations of the 3 different salient term extraction methods and the embeddings, the data increased by a factor of 9. Analysing different intrinsic features (code, in-line comments and Markdown narrative) of the notebook further increased the data by a factor of 4. Therefore, the data size consisted of 37,764 different combinations that were analysed to retrieve the domains. In other words, a notebook had 36 different variations of domains due to 4 intrinsic features, 3 different salient term extraction methods and 3 different embedding models were being analysed. However, the ground truth (i.e. domain) remained the same across all the 36 variations. See Figure 8 for the visualisation of all the variations for a particular notebook.

Figure 8: All The 36 Variations of a Jupyter Notebook

Figure 9, shows the most frequently highest ranked domains by cosine similarity for combinations containing all the intrinsic features combined. That is, for a notebook where code, in-line comments and Markdown narrative were all considered, these domains had the highest cosine similarity with respect to the content of that notebook. It can be seen that there is a mix of problem-related domains like image, time series analysis, data visualization etc., as well as, solution-related domains like linear regression, binary classification, neural networks etc.

Figure 9: Highest Ranked Domains by Cosine Similarity For Combinations Containing all the Intrinsic Features

Table 1, shows the $P@k$ (where $k = 3$) for the different intrinsic features of a notebook across all the pairs of embedding models and the term extraction models. From the table, it can be inferred that the Markdown narrative and all contents combined of a notebook, on average across all embeddings and term type, had the highest relative $P@k$ score equal to 0.0844 while the in-line comments had the lowest average equal to 0.0786. BERT achieved $P@k$ scores of 0.100 to 0.150 across different intrinsic features which was higher than GloVe (0.040 to 0.100) and Word2Vec (0.040 to 0.080). Table 2 shows the pairwise t-test in differences of the average and it can be seen that at 5% significance, the difference between the average $P@k$ scores of different intrinsic features are not significant. Therefore, it cannot be inferred that one intrinsic feature performs better than the other. Additionally, it was found that large majority of the notebooks' combinations (i.e. 21,996 combinations) contained less than 3 Kaggle tags (see Figure 5) indicating that the $P@k$ score was calculated only for 15,768 combinations and the remainder were directly evaluated qualitatively.

Table 1: P@k Scores Across All Pairs of Embeddings and Term Extraction for Different Intrinsic Features

embedding-term type	all contents combined	code	in-line comment	Markdown narrative
BERT-BOW	0.120	0.120	0.140	0.100
BERT-LDA	0.120	0.100	0.120	0.100
BERT-TFIDF	0.120	0.100	0.150	0.100
GloVe-BOW	0.060	0.040	0.040	0.080
GloVe-LDA	0.060	0.100	0.060	0.100
GloVe-TFIDF	0.080	0.080	0.050	0.080
Word2Vec-BOW	0.060	0.060	0.040	0.060
Word2Vec-LDA	0.060	0.060	0.060	0.080
Word2Vec-TFIDF	0.080	0.080	0.050	0.060
Average	0.084	0.082	0.079	0.084

Table 2: Pairwise Significance T-Tests Between Intrinsic Features ($p < 0.05$)

Comparison	Mean Difference	P-value	Significant
all contents combined - code	0.0022	0.7287	No
all contents combined - in-line comment	0.0056	0.4560	No
all contents combined - Markdown narrative	-0.0000	1.0000	No
code - in-line comment	0.0033	0.7440	No
code - Markdown narrative	-0.0022	0.7287	No
in-line comment - Markdown narrative	-0.0056	0.6367	No

Table 3 is derived from Table 1 and it shows the pairwise t-test in differences of the average of $P@k$ amongst the embedding models. The positive and significant difference in the mean difference for the BERT with respect to GloVe and Word2Vec shows that it is the best performing model for creating embeddings at 5% significance. Table 4, which is also derived from Table 1, indicates that there is no significant differences in average performance of $P@k$ across different salient term extraction models. Therefore, no conclusion regarding the best performing model can be derived from this table.

Table 3: Pairwise Significance T-Tests Between Embedding Models ($p < 0.05$)

Comparison	Mean Difference	P-value	Significant
BERT - GloVe	0.0467	0.0000*	Yes
BERT - Word2Vec	0.0533	0.0000*	Yes
GloVe - Word2Vec	0.0067	0.3481	No

Note: * indicates statistical significance at $p < 0.05$

Table 4: Pairwise Significance T-Tests Between Salient Term Extraction Models ($p < 0.05$)

Comparison	Mean Difference	P-value	Significant
BOW - LDA	-0.0083	0.5060	No
BOW - TFIDF	-0.0092	0.4908	No
LDA - TFIDF	-0.0008	0.9396	No

Moving from the quantitative analysis, the results of the LLM assessment can be found in Figure 10. The LLM was used to answer the question pertaining to the relevance of the predicted domains with respect to the contents of the notebooks, as well as specificity of the predicted domains. These figures (i.e. Fig. 10a and 10b) were created by matching keywords revealing a connotation of relevance and specificity to the LLM responses via regular expressions. For example, LLM responses were matched against keywords like highly relevant and very relevant to classify the LLM response as highly relevant. Regular expression were chosen because the LLM was prompted to output such keywords as its response (see Appendix Section 11.1).

Figure 10a shows an overview of the frequency of how often was a domain, predicted with the highest cosine similarity, relevant. Relevance measures whether the predicted domain is actually related to the notebook’s content, while specificity measures how precise or granular the predicted domain is for the given content. These two dimensions are evaluated separately as a domain can be relevant but too general (low specificity), or highly specific but completely incorrect (low relevance). Evidently, image was the most predicted domain with the highest similarity and it was deemed relevant for more than 10,000 different combinations. It is clear that most of the notebook’s contents were relevant or partially relevant with respect to its predicted primary domain. There were some notebooks that were titled unclear/not relevant, as seen in the graph for time series analysis because these notebooks were not related to the predicted domain at all. For example, a notebook titled `tensorflow-decision-forests-tfdf-titanic` was labelled wrongly as time series analysis and the LLM response was - "No, the notebook focuses on Titanic data analysis and feature engineering, not time series analysis. Domains like data analysis are too broad; specific domains like Titanic classification are more appropriate.", thus leading to a unclear/not relevant tag. After manually verifying the LLM responses for the different combinations, it was concluded that the LLM responses were reliable. Due to large size of the dataset, a subset of 103 notebooks, with all possible combinations of intrinsic features, different salient term extraction and embedding models, were analysed manually. The size of the subset was determined according to the Cochran’s formula where the acceptable margin of error was 2% and the t-value at 99% confidence level for a population size of 37,764 (i.e. total number of combinations) for rigorous testing [47].

In Figure 10a, the four-point scale (highly relevant, very relevant, relevant, unclear/not relevant) uses three positive and one negative category for practical reasons based on the LLM response patterns observed. Multiple positive categories were needed because the LLM responses showed clear differences between levels of good predictions. Some domains were perfect matches, others were good but broad, and some were acceptable but not ideal. These differences matter for understanding how well the model works. Only one negative category was sufficient because when predictions were wrong, they were clearly wrong with no meaningful differences between types of errors. A domain was either right for the notebook or it wasn’t - there was no useful way to split "wrong" predictions, thus only one category was included.

Furthermore, Figure 10b shows the variations in the specificity of the predicted domain. There are also signs of unclear tags for all the domains. For domains like time series analysis it can be seen that the LLM deemed majority of the responses as too general with respect to the contents of the notebooks indicating that these notebooks not only belong to the domain of time series but a more specific sub-domain of it. However, domains like image were deemed appropriately specific for most of its instances. Manual verification revealed that the LLM was correct in deeming some domains as too general. For example, a particular variation of the notebook titled `long-short-term-memory-with-pytorch` contained information about deep learning and neural networks rather than being about predicted domain of time series analysis. The LLM response for this notebook’s variation was "The domain time series analysis is not relevant; the notebook focuses on deep learning, neural networks, and PyTorch. Domains are too broad; more specific topics like neural networks or deep learning are appropriate.". It was also found that in notebooks like `bitcoin-trend-prediction-model-tensorflow`, the domain was not relevant and thus the

specificity of domain was not assessed and thus leading to an unclear tag, the LLM response for this notebook was "the domain image is not relevant; the notebook focuses on time series prediction, neural networks, and financial data. Domains like finance or time series are more precise."

There were some caveats found with the usage of pre-trained models for embeddings. Firstly, for model like `fse/glove-wiki-gigaword-100` which is trained solely on tweets struggled with creating embeddings for terms like `dtype` which is a reserved keyword for describing "how the bytes in the fixed-size block of memory corresponding to an array item should be interpreted" [11] because it was not available in the training data for the GloVe model and thus, the resulting embedding vector was a zero vector. Secondly, due to the large training dataset of these models, they lack specificity in their embeddings. For example, using `bert-base-uncased` to create embeddings for `torch`, `numpy`, `tensorflow`, `light`, `bulb` and `pytorch` resulted in the Figure 11 when mapped out in two-dimensions using Principal Component Analysis (PCA). It is evident that `torch` is associated more with `light` and `bulb` rather than with other Python libraries. This suggests that the embeddings created by BERT is more generic rather than specific to the context of Jupyter Notebooks.

RQ1: BERT embeddings with any salient term extraction method (LDA, BOW, TF-IDF) significantly outperformed Word2Vec and GloVe embeddings, with mean differences of 0.0467 and 0.0533 respectively ($p < 0.05$). However, no significant differences were found between different intrinsic features (code, comments, Markdown narrative) or salient term extraction methods. The LLM qualitative assessment revealed that image was the most frequently predicted domain (>10,000 combinations) with high relevance scores, while domains like time series analysis were often deemed too general by the LLM evaluation.

LLM Assessment of Domain Relevance

(a) LLM Assessment of Domain Relevance

LLM Assessment of Domain Specificity

(b) LLM Assessment of Domain Specificity

Figure 10: LLM Assessments of Predicted Domains Across Notebooks

Figure 11: torch is Associated More With light and bulb Compared To Python Libraries

6.2 RQ2

Figure 12 shows the correlation matrix between the independent variables that were used in the multinomial logistic regression. The correlation matrix helped in revealing the multicollinearity issues between the variables and it is evident from this figure that the variables num_lines and cyclomatic_complexity; num_functions and cyclomatic_complexity; and num_lines and num_functions were all correlated with a correlation coefficient higher than or equal to 0.8. Therefore, the variables num_lines describing the number of lines of code in a notebook and num_functions describing the number of functions in a notebook were removed and the logistic regression was done without them.

Subsequently, VIF scores revealed that all the variables were below 10 and thus, no additional variables were removed. It can be seen from Table 5 that the initial correlation analysis was sufficient in removing multicollinearity as the highest VIF score recorded was 2.12 which is well below 10.

Figure 12: Correlation Matrix For the Independent Variables in Logistic Regression

Table 5: VIF for Features in Descending Order

Feature	VIF
num_classes	2.12
cyclomatic_complexity	2.08
tensor_lib_torch	1.75
tensor_lib_tensorflow	1.67
op_transpose	1.48
op_concatenate	1.30
op_multiply	1.29
op_matmul	1.29
op_gather	1.27
op_stack	1.26

Domains containing fewer than 5 notebook samples were excluded from the logistic regression analysis, as this sample size was considered insufficient for reliable statistical inference [45]. Furthermore, the target variable (i.e. domain) was taken from the variations of notebooks where all the intrinsic features were combined (i.e code, in-line comments and the Markdown narra-

tive, altogether). The reason to consider only this variation was to ensure that all the notebooks were included in the dataset and it showed promising results in the first research question in domain prediction. For example, if the top domains were chosen from the variations of notebooks where only Markdown narrative was considered, it would imply loss of data because notebooks like `create-model-h5-dengan-tensorflow` in the dataset had no Markdown narrative and thus, no corresponding top domain. The dataset was reduced by 75% by retaining only the combined variations and excluding notebooks with individual intrinsic features (code, comments, or Markdown narratives separately). This reduction enhanced computational efficiency while eliminating redundant variations of identical notebooks, thereby reducing overfitting risk and improving model convergence. The parameters chosen for running the logistic regression were `max_iter=2000` for better convergence and `class_weight='balanced'` to avoid having bias for one domain over another.

Table 6 shows the values of coefficients across domains whose features were significant with p-value < 0.05 . The results reveal that domain specialization determines code pattern predictability. It can be seen that for domain like image that was the most frequent domain, there were no significant features indicating that notebooks belonging to this domain did not follow any correlation with any code metrics in the regression. Domains like image encompass too much programming diversity to be reliably distinguished by code features. On the contrary, the text domain had the highest count of significant variables showing a strong correlation with metrics like `op_pool` corresponding to the pooling operations of the tensors; the coefficient recorded for this variable was -2.32 indicating that as the log-odds of the notebook belonging to text domain decreases by 2.32 units if pooling operations are introduced in the notebook, while holding all other variables/metrics constant. This can be verified in real-world scenarios where pooling is done to reduce the dimensions of feature maps and commonly used in convolutional neural networks (CNN) to work primarily with spatial images rather than text [41]. More specific domains like the computer vision domain showed a significant negative association with NumPy library usage with a coefficient of -0.82, suggesting that computer vision notebooks are less likely to rely heavily on NumPy compared to other domains. This finding reflects the evolution of computer vision workflows toward specialized deep learning frameworks like PyTorch and TensorFlow libraries, which provide optimised tensor-related operations and GPU acceleration support that is computationally faster than NumPy-based implementations for complex vision tasks [50]. Similarly, coefficients of different variables can also be interpreted with respect to the domains.

The performance of the logistic regression model was done using balanced accuracy and macro-average F1, as described in Section 5.2. Table 7 shows the recall and F1 score per class, which are used to calculate the overall resulting balanced accuracy and macro-average F1. It can be seen that the model performs poorly with a low balanced accuracy of 0.144 and a low macro-average F1 of 0.022. It can be seen that the model recall for predicting the domain movies and tv shows is 1.00 indicating it recalls all the samples perfectly but, there are only 5 samples for this domain and hence its reliability is questionable. On the contrary, the model recalls 0.00 for the image domain showing poor performance. The poor recall can be linked back to Table 6 results where the domain, image, had no significant coefficients, showing that the model struggled to find a meaningful pattern across the samples for this domain [24]. This trend is evident for domains with large samples from image to model comparison. For F1 scores per domain, a similar pattern was followed for domains and there were more sparse values (i.e. 0.00) across the domains indicating that the model struggled with balancing the precision and recall. The best F1 score recorded was for model explainability domain with the value of 0.119 but, it was still far from the best performance (i.e. 1.00). Ogundimu et al. found that rule of thumb should be at least 20 samples in order to eliminate bias in regression coefficients, and therefore, a line separating the adequate domains with enough sample size can be seen in the table [45]. The threshold of 20 is reliable for this thesis because as seen in domains like movies and tv shows that contain only 5 samples, an excellent recall of 1.00 is still an unreliable result.

Table 7: Performance Metrics Across Domains with At Least 5 Samples

Domain	Number of Samples	Balanced Accuracy	Macro-Average F1
Overall	8447	0.144	0.022
		Recall	F1
image	2963	0.00	0.000
time series analysis	2767	0.00	0.000
data visualization	588	0.00	0.000
image segmentation	486	0.00	0.000
text generation	373	0.00	0.000
model comparison	323	0.00	0.000
image classification	224	0.02	0.025
binary classification	219	0.02	0.024
model explainability	162	0.17	0.119
image generator	131	0.06	0.034
recommender systems	111	0.18	0.048
text pre-processing	100	0.08	0.021
wandb	82	0.05	0.014
data cleaning	80	0.05	0.017
linear regression	74	0.21	0.108
neural networks	42	0.36	0.065
transfer learning	30	0.00	0.000
computer vision	24	0.17	0.070
selective kernel	23	0.00	0.000
image augmentation	23	0.17	0.024
gradient boosting	21	0.20	0.014
exploratory data analysis	12	0.67	0.017
weight standardization	12	0.67	0.043
eyes and vision	11	0.00	0.000
gpu	10	0.00	0.000
convolution	10	0.50	0.016
feature engineering	9	0.00	0.000
religion and belief systems	9	0.00	0.000
decision tree	6	0.00	0.000
heart conditions	6	0.00	0.000
movies and tv shows	5	1.00	0.061
text	5	0.00	0.000

Raising the minimum sample size per domain from at least 5 to at least 20 samples according to Ogundimu et al. gave the results as shown in Table 8 and now the balanced accuracy and macro-average F1 improved in their scores. However, the individual scores remained similar per domain. This further confirmed that the model struggled with finding meaningful patterns for many domains and that there was no clear pattern in notebooks belonging to certain domains.

It was also found that num_classes had many outliers across domains. In Figure 13a, outliers can be seen as black dots in the 5 highest occurring domains; however, once the outliers are removed using the formula $Q3+1.5\times IQR$, where Q3 is the 75th percentiles and IQR is the is a measure of variability, based on dividing a data set into quartiles, it can be seen that the number of classes for these domains is 0 [26, 61]. The outlier notebooks belonging to these domains contain high number of classes but most of the notebooks do not. This can create a unreliable correlation between a certain domain from Figure 13 and num_classes as this correlation may imply for all the notebooks belonging to that domain even though num_classes is 0 for most of them.

Table 8: Performance Metrics Across Domains with At Least 20 Samples

Domain	Number of Samples	Balanced Accuracy	Macro-Average F1
Overall	8352	0.175	0.046
		Recall	F1
image	2963	0.00	0.000
time series analysis	2767	0.00	0.000
data visualization	588	0.01	0.022
image segmentation	486	0.04	0.073
text generation	373	0.06	0.077
model comparison	323	0.00	0.000
image classification	224	0.18	0.129
binary classification	219	0.09	0.078
model explainability	162	0.10	0.119
image generator	131	0.18	0.034
recommender systems	111	0.11	0.048
text pre-processing	100	0.32	0.071
wandb	82	0.20	0.044
data cleaning	80	0.40	0.055
linear regression	74	0.33	0.082
neural networks	42	0.20	0.046
transfer learning	30	0.00	0.000
computer vision	24	0.33	0.017
selective kernel	23	0.17	0.020
image augmentation	23	0.67	0.051
gradient boosting	21	0.40	0.016

Figure 13: Comparison Of num_classes Feature Distribution Across 5 Most Frequent Domains

A caveat found while running the experiments was that the AST parsing (to obtain tensor operations) failed in notebooks that had iPython magic commands [7]. These magic commands are specific to Jupyter Notebooks and they perform certain capabilities. For example, `%timeit` is used to time how long a cell in the notebook runs for. A solution was this to filter out such lines as they did not have any effect on the extraction of the tensor operations. However, the problem with

ASTs persisted due to out-of-order cells with hidden states, where some cells were removed causing a disruption in the order and also bad practices like global and implicit dependencies [52]. Lastly, another caveat was the potential bias that was propagated from the previous research question in identifying domains. That is, there was a subjective analysis done to evaluate the domains and thus this was prone to human error and bias.

RQ2: The multinomial logistic regression achieved poor performance with a balanced accuracy of 0.144 and macro-average F1 of 0.022 when using 32 domains with ≥ 5 samples each. Poor results persisted when the sample threshold was increased from 5 to ≥ 20 . Multicollinearity analysis revealed strong correlations (≥ 0.8) between `num_lines` and `cyclomatic_complexity`; `num_lines` and `num_functions`; and `num_functions` and `cyclomatic_complexity`, necessitating feature removal. Domains with significant feature correlations included text (12 significant features), data cleaning (14 significant features), and computer vision (13 significant features), while the most frequent domain image had 0 significant features, indicating no meaningful code complexity patterns for image-related notebooks.

7 Discussions

7.1 Domain Classification Performance and Model Robustness

The results for RQ1 demonstrate that while the proposed pipeline can successfully extract salient terms and classify notebook domains, the quantitative performance metrics reveal significant challenges. The extremely low $P@k$ scores across all combinations (with averages ranging from 0.079 to 0.084) initially suggest poor performance. However, this metric’s limitations become apparent when considering that 21,996 out of 37,764 combinations (i.e. 58.2%) contained fewer than 3 Kaggle tags, making $P@k$ evaluation impossible for the vast majority of cases. This finding is particularly significant as it exposes a fundamental limitation in using ground truth tags like Kaggle tags for evaluation - the sparse and inconsistent nature of user-generated tags creates an evaluation bottleneck that may not accurately reflect the model’s true capabilities.

The qualitative analysis using LLMs provides a more nuanced picture of performance. Figure 10a reveals that the most frequently predicted domain, image, was deemed relevant in over 10,000 combinations, suggesting that the embedding-based cosine similarity approach successfully identified semantically coherent domains. The LLM evaluation’s reliability was confirmed through manual verification of all 36 possible variations of a subset of 103 notebooks, calculated via Cochran’s formula, providing confidence in the qualitative assessment approach.

7.2 Embedding Model Performance and Semantic Representation

The statistical analysis in Table 3 provides clear evidence that BERT embeddings significantly outperformed both GloVe and Word2Vec embeddings ($p < 0.05$), with mean differences of 0.0467 and 0.0533 respectively. This superior performance can be attributed to BERT’s contextual understanding capabilities from a large corpus [20], which are particularly valuable when dealing with technical terminology and domain-specific language common in Jupyter Notebooks. Similar results were found by Lu et al. [37] where transformer-based models like BERT achieved a significant improvement than commonly used vector embeddings like Word2Vec for labelling text datasets. However, the analysis also revealed critical limitations in using pre-trained embeddings for specialized domains as seen in Figure 11, where the model struggled to pair torch alongside other tensor-related libraries but rather paired it with light and bulb. This finding suggests that the embeddings created by BERT are more generic rather than specific to the context of tensor-themed Jupyter Notebooks.

No significant differences were found between different intrinsic features (code, in-line comments, Markdown narrative) or salient term extraction methods (LDA, BOW, TFIDF). This suggests that the choice of content type or term extraction method is less critical than the embedding approach used, simplifying future implementations of the pipeline.

7.3 Code Complexity Analysis and Domain Relationship

The results for RQ2 revealed poor performance of the multinomial logistic regression approach to establish meaningful relationships between code complexity metrics and notebook domains with a balanced accuracy of 0.144 and macro-average F1 of 0.022. This poor performance suggests that code structural features alone are insufficient for determining notebook domains.

The coefficient analysis in Table 6 provides insights into why this approach failed. The most frequent domain, image, showed zero significant features, indicating no discernible patterns in code complexity for image-related notebooks. However, some domains did show significant correlations with specific features. The text domain exhibited the highest number of significant features (i.e. 12), including strong negative coefficients for pooling operations (-2.32) and tensor library usage. This makes intuitive sense, as text processing typically involves different tensor operations compared to image processing, which commonly uses pooling layers in convolutional neural networks [41, 40].

7.4 Multicollinearity and Feature Selection

The multicollinearity analysis (Figure 12) revealed expected correlations between related metrics, particularly between `num_classes`, `num_lines` and `cyclomatic_complexity` (≥ 0.8), necessitating feature removal. This finding aligns with the findings of Smith et al., showing that lines of code and complexity metrics often exhibit strong linear relationships [2]. The successful removal of multicollinearity, evidenced by all VIF scores falling below 10 after feature removal (Table 5), demonstrates the importance of proper feature selection in regression analysis.

The presence of outliers in features like `num_classes` (Figure 13a) further complicated the analysis. The removal of outliers revealed that most notebooks contained few class definitions amongst the most popular domains, suggesting that OOP patterns are not commonly used in tensor-related notebooks for such domains. This finding provides valuable insights into coding practices when working with tensors for certain popular domains.

7.5 Implications for Practitioners and Researchers

The superior performance of BERT embeddings over Word2Vec and GloVe provides practical guidance for practitioners developing automated notebook classification systems. Organisations or individuals managing large repositories of Jupyter Notebooks, such as Kaggle, GitHub, or internal corporate data science platforms, can leverage these findings to improve their content organisation and discovery systems. However, the semantic struggles identified (e.g., `torch` being associated with lighting rather than Python library) suggest that practitioners should prioritise domain-specific fine-tuning or training their own model when implementing such systems.

The poor performance of code metrics on predicting domains suggests that traditional software engineering code metrics may not translate directly to the domain that the notebooks belong to. Rather, the current practices may need to incorporate semantic analysis approaches to better

understand the domain, in combination to the statistical methods.

8 Threats to Validity

8.1 External

Limited Generalisability: This study was conducted exclusively on Kaggle notebooks, which may not be representative of the broader Jupyter Notebook ecosystem. Kaggle users tend to focus on competitive machine learning and data science tasks, potentially creating a bias toward specific programming patterns. Results may not generalise to notebooks used in academic research, enterprise environments, or other specialised contexts where different coding practices, libraries, and domain focuses are prevalent. A solution is to consider a dataset across diverse notebook repositories such as GitHub, academic platforms, or industry-specific environments.

Pre-Trained Embedding Model Limitations: The pre-trained embedding models (BERT, GloVe, Word2Vec) used for semantic analysis were trained on general-purpose datasets, as described previously, that may not adequately represent specialised scientific or technical vocabulary commonly found in tensor-related notebooks. This creates a systematic bias where domains with terminology closer to common language patterns may achieve better classification accuracy than highly specialised domains.

Temporal Validity: The pre-trained models and evaluation frameworks used in this study represent notebooks for a specific timeline. As embedding technologies evolve and new domain-specific models emerge, the relative performance rankings observed in this study may change. Additionally, the rapid evolution of machine learning libraries and coding practices means that new domains may emerge and the code complexity metrics and their relationships to domains may shift over time.

Scalability and Computational Resource Requirements: The study’s methodology requires significant computational resources for large-scale embedding generation and LLM-based evaluation. This creates barriers to scalability, replication and validation, particularly for researchers in resource-constrained environments. The computational requirements may limit the practical applicability of the approach for real-time or large-scale deployment scenarios.

8.2 Internal

Ground Truth Labelling and Evaluation Challenges: User-generated metadata is inherently subjective and inconsistent, with significant human bias and noise [43]. This inconsistency in ground truth labelling can lead to misleading performance assessments and makes it difficult to distinguish between genuine domain classification errors by the models and annotation inconsistencies. To mitigate this, more sophisticated approaches like annotator agreement can be used that evaluates how consistently annotators label the same data [29, 51].

LLM Evaluation Bias and Consistency: The use of LLMs for qualitative evaluation introduces internal validity concerns. LLMs may exhibit systematic biases based on their training data, potentially favoring certain domains or types of content over others [5]. The consistency and reliability of LLM-based qualitative assessments have not been thoroughly validated against human expert judgment, creating uncertainty about the accuracy of domain relevance and specificity evaluations [69]. Additionally, the computational cost of extensive LLM evaluation may have limited the scope of validation performed.

Sample Size Limitations: As discussed previously, the poor performance of code complexity metrics in domain prediction raises questions about whether the sample size and feature representation were adequate to detect meaningful relationships despite increasing the threshold of samples from 5 to 20 per domain. The low explanatory power suggests that either the code metrics chosen are not predictive of domain, or there indeed does not exist a relationship. However, this can be concretely verified by including a larger dataset and verifying whether the results change.

Error Propagation: As mentioned before, the usage of pre-trained models may propagate errors due to their general-purpose datasets and lack of specific knowledge specific to tensor-themed notebooks. The embeddings models (BERT, Word2Vec, GloVe) used in the first research question can potentially cause errors in predicting the domains that is propagated to the second research question causing errors in correlation analysis.

9 Conclusion and Future Work

A widespread usage of Jupyter Notebooks was identified in fields like literate programming [27] and a research gap was discovered with respect to the domain classification of such notebooks. Prior research was done majorly on source-code classification [8, 39]; however, through this research, the focus was on intrinsic features - code, in-line comments and Markdown narrative - of the notebooks for classification. This thesis further explores the relation between code metrics and the domain that the notebook belongs to.

RQ1 focused on domain classification of notebooks using different salient term extraction methods and embedding models across different intrinsic features of a notebook. Answering RQ1, BERT embeddings with any salient term extraction method (LDA, BOW, TF-IDF) significantly outperformed Word2Vec and GloVe embeddings, with mean differences of 0.0467 and 0.0533 respectively with p-value < 0.05 . However, no significant differences in performance were found between different intrinsic features (code, comments, Markdown narrative) or salient term extraction methods. The LLM qualitative assessment revealed that image was the most frequently predicted domain ($> 10,000$ combinations) with high relevance scores, while domains like time series analysis were often deemed too general by the LLM evaluation for domain specificity. Critical limitations were identified in usage of pre-trained embeddings, where torch was associated with lighting rather than Python library, suggesting embeddings are more generic rather than specific to tensor-themed notebooks.

RQ2 focused on analysing the correlation between the code metrics of a notebook and the domain of that particular notebook. Answering RQ2, results show that code complexity metrics are insufficient for determining notebook domains, achieving only a balanced accuracy of 0.144 and macro-average F1 of 0.022. The most frequent domain, image, had no significant metrics with respect to the domains of the notebook, indicating no discernible patterns in code complexity to determine domain. However, certain specific domains like computer vision showed a negative correlation between the NumPy library usage which further strengthens the argument that computer vision tasks requires libraries like Pytorch and TensorFlow that allow for GPU acceleration. A critical limitation highlighted the usage of iPython magic commands, that caused a failure in AST parsing to retrieve necessary information about tensor operations in the Jupyter Notebooks.

To conclude, the findings show that BERT is a better model than Word2Vec and GloVe for created vector embeddings for domain classification. However, fine-tuning of embedding models is needed. No significant differences were found in performance of the intrinsic features in the context of Jupyter notebooks. Code complexity metrics prove inadequate for domain prediction, highlighting the need for semantic in combination with structural approaches in notebook classification.

Future work can explore domain-specific embedding model training using technical documentation, academic papers, and specialized codebases to address the semantic confusion issues identified with general-purpose embeddings. Cross-platform validation beyond Kaggle to include GitHub, academic platforms, and enterprise environments can enhance generalisability and reduce platform-specific biases. Hybrid approaches combining semantic analysis with statistical approaches, rather than statistical correlation of code complexity and domain, can be investigated for improved classification performance. Temporal analysis exploring how notebook domains evolve over time can identify emerging application areas and track adoption patterns of new tensor libraries. Finally, more robust evaluation methodologies for weakly supervised domain classification can address the limitations identified with $P@k$ metric in sparse tag environments, potentially developing domain-specific evaluation frameworks better suited for notebook classification. Such frameworks could implement a hierarchical evaluation approach that accounts for semantic similarity between domains—for example, when the ground truth domain of a notebook is deep learning and the prediction is neural networks, the evaluation metric could assign a score of 0.8 rather than strictly penalising it completely with 0.0.

10 Data Availability

The implementation for this thesis can be found at
<https://github.com/ummtushar/domain-analysis-nlp-thesis>

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11 Appendix

11.1 Prompt for Qualitative Analysis

```
1 prompt = (  
2     f"Domain to evaluate: {domain}\n\n"  
3     "Notebook Content:\n"  
4 )  
5  
6 if code_sample:  
7     prompt += f"CODE:\n{code_sample}\n\n"  
8  
9 if narrative_sample:  
10    prompt += f"MARKDOWN:\n{narrative_sample}\n\n"  
11  
12 prompt += (  
13     "Question: Based on the notebook content, is the given "  
14     "domain relevant to this notebook and determine whether "  
15     "it is highly relevant, partially relevant or just "  
16     "relevant- and explain why? How specific & precise are "  
17     "the domains? Are they too general (e.g. data analysis) "  
18     "or appropriate specific (e.g. NLP) or too specific "  
19     "(e.g. tensor)- choose one and explain?"  
20 )
```

11.2 System Instruction for Qualitative Analysis

```
1 "role": "system",  
2 "content": "You are a helpful assistant. Your task is to understand the content of  
a Jupyter Notebook and analyse the domains predicted for that notebook. After  
doing so, you are to make a judgment on whether the predicted domains are  
indeed relevant to the content and whether the domain is specific . Answer all  
the questions in plain text keep your response concise."
```

11.3 LLM Multi-Threading Implementation

Snippet of using multithreading where the notebooks are processed in parallel using a thread pool with `max_workers` set to 5 as default. The libraries used are `concurrent.futures` and `threading`.

```
1 with concurrent.futures.ThreadPoolExecutor(max_workers=MAX_WORKERS) as executor:  
2     future_to_index = {  
3         executor.submit(process_notebook, row, nb_contents_dir): row.name  
4         for _, row in chunk.iterrows()  
5     }  
6  
7 with tqdm(total=len(future_to_index), desc="Processing notebooks") as pbar:  
8     for future in concurrent.futures.as_completed(future_to_index):  
9         index, llm_response = future.result()  
10        df.at[index, 'llm_relevance'] = llm_response  
11        pbar.update(1)
```

11.4 AST for Tensor Complexities

```
1 # Pre-filter lines that are obviously not standard Python (e.g., IPython magics)  
lines = code_content.splitlines()  
3 python_lines = [line for line in lines if not (line.strip().startswith('%') or line  
4 .strip().startswith('!'))]  
5 parsable_code_content = "\n".join(python_lines)  
6  
7 if not parsable_code_content.strip():  
8     # If all lines were magics, there were some errors or empty, no AST parsing  
9     needed
```

```

8     pass
9 else:
10    tree = ast.parse(parsable_code_content)
11
12    class TensorOpVisitor(ast.NodeVisitor):
13        def __init__(self, ops_list):
14            self.tensor_ops_set = set(ops_list)
15            self.op_counts = {op: 0 for op in ops_list}
16            self.total_op_count = 0
17
18            def visit_Call(self, node): #extract tensor operations as keywords
19                func_name = None
20                if isinstance(node.func, ast.Name): # e.g., add(...)
21                    func_name = node.func.id
22                elif isinstance(node.func, ast.Attribute): # e.g., np.add(...) or
23                    tensor.add(...)
24                    func_name = node.func.attr
25
26                if func_name and func_name.lower() in self.tensor_ops_set:
27                    op_key = func_name.lower() # tensor_ops are already lowercase
28                    self.op_counts[op_key] += 1
29                    self.total_op_count += 1
30
31                self.generic_visit(node)
32
33    visitor = TensorOpVisitor(tensor_ops)
34    visitor.visit(tree)
35
36    num_tensor_ops = visitor.total_op_count
37    for op_name, count in visitor.op_counts.items():
38        if count > 0:
39            tensor_op_usage[f"op_{op_name}"] = 1

```